

Screening of different mustard varieties for resistance against mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.)

Shravan Lal Jat, B.L. Jat and R.K. Choudhary

Dept. of Entomology, S.K.N. College of Agril., Rajasthan Agril. University, Bikaner Campus, Jobner-303 329, Rajasthan

(Received: September, 2006; Revised: December, 2006; Accepted: February, 2007)

Mustard, *Brassica juncea* (Linn.) Czern. & Coss. is an important oilseed crop of family Cruciferae. It is mainly grown in *rabi* season as oilseed, condiment and medicinal crop. The green leaves and stems of mustard are good source of green vegetables and fodder. The oil content in seeds ranges from 32 to 42%, used for edible purposes. In India, important mustard growing state are Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, West Bengal, Punjab and Assam. The area under the crop in Rajasthan was 1.19 m. ha with an annual production of 1.17 m. tones and average productivity of 989 kg/ha during the year 2002-2003. Mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* Kalt. is one of the most serious pest of this crop (Rai, 1976) causing 9.0-95.0% losses in seed yield and on an average 15.0% loss in its oil yield. Both nymph and adult stages of this pest cause quantitative and qualitative losses to crop. In integrated pest management programme growing of resistance varieties against insect, is one of the most important tool in the management of aphid without additional cost.

The field experiment was conducted during *rabi* 2003-04 at S. K. N. College of Agriculture, Jobner- Rajasthan. The experiment was laid out in Randomize Block Design with three replications and 10 cultivars. The plot size was 4 x 3 m² with row to row and plant to plant distance of 30 cm and 10 cm, respectively. The crop was sown on 5th November 2003. The observations on the population of aphid were recorded at weekly interval from the appearance of aphid to harvesting of the crop. The aphids were counted visually on upper 10 cm shoot of five randomly selected tagged plants (Bakhetia and Sandhu, 1973). The total phenols and free amino acids were estimated from leaf of the plant at the time of peak aphid population. Total phenol and free amino acids were estimated as per standard method. The simple correlation was computed between aphid population and biochemical parameters.

None of the variety was found completely free from aphid infestation. Aphid infestation started from first week of

January and reached to its peak in the first week of February and continued up to middle of March. The minimum mean aphid population (16 aphids/plant) was observed on variety T-59 (Varuna), while maximum (56 aphids/plant) on RZM-1359. The population was comparatively less on varieties T-59 (Varuna) and Bio-902 could be categorized as least preferred. On varieties viz., TM-4, PCR-7, RH-30, RH-781 and PBR-91 the aphid population was of middle order and thus categorized as moderately preferred. The aphid population was more on varieties GM-2, JM-1 and RZM-1359 which was recognized as highly preferred varieties. The present investigation corroborates with those of Vir *et al.* (1990), Jat *et al.* (1993) and Takar *et al.* (2003) who observed that varieties T-59 (Varuna), Bio-902 and PCR-7 were highly resistant to mustard aphid.

The morphological character of plant viz., plant height @ = - 0.988), siliqua/plant @ = - 0.946) and seeds/siliqua @ = - 0.965) were negatively correlated with the peak aphid population. An increase in aphid population was responsible for reduction of plant height, siliqua/plant and seeds/siliqua. These results are in conformity with those of Malik and Deen (1998).

The total phenols was negatively correlated @ = -0.990) while, free amino acids was positively correlated @ = 0.992) with aphid population. The minimum aphid population was recorded in variety T-59 (Varuna) which had highest of total phenols and lowest of free amino acids (4.52 % and 1.30 %) whereas, the maximum aphid population was found in variety RZM-1359 which had lowest of total phenols and highest of free amino acids (2.97 % and 2.18 %).

Sachan and Sachan (1991) and Ram Dhari *et al.* (1995) also reported the negative correlation between total phenols and mustard aphid population and Malik (1988) reported positively correlation between free amino acids and aphid population.

Table 1 Weekly mean aphid, *L. erysimi* population/plant (10 cm top shoot) on different mustard varieties

Variety	08.01.04	15.01.04	22.01.04	29.01.04	05.02.04	12.02.04	19.02.04	26.02.04	05.03.04	Mean
PBR-91	7.46 (2.82)	23.60 (4.90)	44.80 (6.72)	68.60 (8.30)	92.93* (9.60)	71.13 (8.44)	36.13 (6.06)	17.46 (4.22)	3.46 (1.99)	40.62
GM-2	8.20 (2.95)	31.00 (5.60)	63.80 (8.01)	74.40 (8.64)	106.93 (10.35)	81.66 (9.05)	39.20 (6.28)	24.80 (5.00)	4.40 (2.21)	48.27
TM-4	5.86 (2.52)	18.60 (4.36)	35.13 (5.96)	51.13 (7.18)	71.46 (8.48)	55.07 (7.44)	25.46 (5.09)	14.40 (3.84)	2.60 (1.76)	31.08
JM-1	9.13 (3.10)	25.80 (5.11)	56.66 (7.55)	72.40 (8.53)	107.93 (10.41)	85.40 (9.26)	44.46 (6.70)	26.40 (5.17)	6.33 (2.61)	48.28
T-59	2.20 (1.64)	7.66 (2.85)	17.66 (4.25)	26.33 (5.17)	46.20 (6.83)	32.00 (5.70)	8.66 (2.99)	1.46 (1.40)	0.00 (0.71)	15.78
RH-781	6.86 (2.71)	24.00 (4.95)	54.40 (7.40)	62.80 (7.95)	84.13 (9.20)	64.67 (8.06)	32.13 (5.70)	18.67 (4.36)	3.40 (1.97)	39.01
PCR-7	5.20 (2.39)	12.26 (3.56)	24.33 (4.98)	38.60 (6.24)	56.00 (7.50)	38.60 (6.24)	16.53 (4.10)	5.33 (2.40)	1.60 (1.45)	22.06
Bio-902	3.00 (1.87)	9.00 (3.08)	20.26 (4.55)	30.80 (5.58)	48.46 (6.99)	34.00 (5.87)	10.20 (3.24)	2.26 (1.64)	1.00 (1.22)	17.67
RZM-1359	11.80 (3.51)	34.53 (5.90)	64.93 (8.08)	84.26 (9.20)	111.66 (10.59)	91.53 (9.59)	50.26 (7.12)	32.60 (5.74)	8.40 (2.98)	55.78
RH-30	6.33 (2.61)	13.40 (3.70)	26.53 (5.19)	40.80 (6.41)	58.53 (7.68)	44.07 (6.67)	22.66 (4.79)	9.20 (3.10)	2.13 (1.62)	24.92
SEm±	0.21	0.26	0.27	0.27	0.28	0.29	0.30	0.28	0.19	-
CD (P=0.005)	0.62	0.77	0.80	0.79	0.83	0.86	0.89	0.89	0.56	-

Figures in parenthesis are root $x+0.5$ transformed values; * = Peak aphid population during the crop season

Table 2 Effect of morphological and biochemical characters of plant on aphid, *L. erysimi* population

Variety	Aphid population	Plant height (cm)	Siliqua/plant	Seeds/siliqua	Total Phenol (%)	Free amino acid (%)
PBR-91	93	140	158	8	3.6	1.8
GM-2	106	134	145	8	3.1	1.9
TM-4	71	143	161	9	4.0	1.6
JM-1	107	133	141	8	3.0	2.0
T-59	96	152	193	11	4.5	1.3
RH-781	84	142	158	8	3.7	1.8
PCR-7	56	147	169	11	4.2	1.4
Bio-902	48	151	180	11	4.4	1.3
RZM-1359	112	131	139	7	2.9	2.1
RH-30	59	146	167	9	4.1	1.4
Correlation coefficient with aphid population		-0.988*	-0.946*	-0.965*	-0.990*	0.992*

* Significant at 5% level

Screening of different mustard varieties for resistance against mustard aphid

References

- Bakhetia, D. R. C. and Sandhu, R. S. 1973. Differential response of *Brassica* species to the aphid (*Lipaphis erysimi* Kalt.) infestation. *Journal of Research Punjab Agricultural University*, 10(3): 272-279.
- Jat, M. C., Sharma, J. K. and Jat, B. L. 1993. The relative incidence of aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.) on some mustard varieties/entries. *Indian Journal of Applied Entomology*, 7: 77-80.
- Malik, R. S. 1988. Role of amino acids in relation to aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.) resistance in cruciferous species. *Journal of Oilseeds Research*, 5 (2): 39-45.
- Malik, Y. P. and Deen, B. 1998. Impact of aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.) intensity on plant growth and seed characters of Indian mustard. *Indian Journal of Entomology*, 60(2): 36-42.
- Rai, B. K. 1976. *Pests of Oilseed Crops in India and their Control*. Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR), New Delhi, pp. 121.
- Ram Dhari, Yadava, T. P., Singh, H. and Rohilla, H. R. 1995. Effect of biochemical and anatomical traits of Indian mustard on mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.) infestation. *Annals of Agricultural Research*, 16 (4): 509-510.
- Sachan, S. K. and Sachan, G. C. 1991. Relation of some biochemical characters of *Brassica juncea* (Coss.) to susceptibility to *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.). *Indian Journal of Entomology*, 53 (2): 218-225.
- Takar, B. L., Deshwal, H. L. and Jat, B. L. 2003. Screening of different varieties/entries of *Brassica juncea* Linn. to mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.) infestation. *Annals of Biology*, 19 (2): 209-212.
- Vir, S., Singh, M. P. and Henry, A. 1990. Yield loss in important cultivars of raya and effect of date of sowing on aphid infestation under arid climate of Rajasthan. *Indian Journal of Entomology*, 52 (4): 541-546.